

Surface roughness evolution of wind turbine blade subject to rain erosion

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A computational model for the prediction of leading edge roughness was developed by relating local fatigue damage to material removal.
- The model predicts surface roughness parameters, erosion depth and mass loss over time.
- Comparison with experimental measurements by an optical surface profilometer was performed for validation.
- The predictions could provide valuable input for estimating energy production losses due to leading edge erosion.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Leading edge erosion of wind turbine blades causes roughening of the blade's surface, leading to a reduction of energy production. This paper presents a computational model for the prediction of the roughness evolution of the blade's surface, based on fatigue damage calculations and rain droplet impact simulations. A novel method for the calculation of material roughness due to multiple random liquid impacts was developed, by considering damage concentration in areas where sharpness due to material removal is formed. Material removal was governed by fatigue damage values. The computational model was compared to roughness measurements from a sample tested in a rain erosion tester. The outputs of this model are 3D surfaces resembling the roughness of the protective coating layer as well as the evolution of surface roughness parameters and mass loss throughout time.

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1. Introduction

The success of the renewable energy transition in Europe depends on the development and expansion of wind energy. For the next decades, large expansion of wind energy is foreseen, especially, of offshore wind energy. It is expected that the global wind power market will reach 69.7 GW by 2027 [1].

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Wind turbines, especially offshore wind turbines, are subject to high permanent loads, including mechanical loading and environmental loading, like moisture, salt and ultraviolet light. As differed from other large structures, like buildings, airplanes or cars, wind turbine maintenance is very expensive and difficult work. While airplanes are checked before and after each flight, and service stations for cars are available everywhere, the inspection, maintenance and repair of an offshore wind turbine requires quite large investments, of the order of several dozens of thousands of euros for each damage case [2]. In [3], several surveys of service teams and wind park owners were evaluated, and the frequencies of var-

ious failure mechanisms of wind turbine blades were estimated. It was demonstrated that leading edge erosion of wind turbine blades is the most often observed damage mechanism of blades [3]. In [2], it was shown that minor damage of blades, mainly, surface erosion, causes up to 10 times higher costs than major damage, like buckling or collapse of a blade.

Therefore, leading edge erosion is a critical problem for the wind energy development, increasing the costs of energy (up to 25% for maintenance [2]), and making wind energy less competitive on the market. There are different estimations on how the erosion of blades influences the energy generation. In [4], the expected loss of AEP (annual energy production) due to erosion is estimated at the level of 1.7%. Christian Bak and colleagues estimated the AEP reduction by 0.5–4% [5]. Law and Koutos [6] reported 1.8–5% reduction. Such a reduction of energy production raises the need for repair, which is rather expensive.

There exist a number of different solutions for blade protection against erosion, among them, ProBlade Collision Barrier by LM Wind Power, 3 M polyurethane coatings and W4600, polyurethane tape by Bergolin, Duromar, Belzona 1331 and Belzona 1381, and many others [8]. These solutions still cannot ensure the required lifetime for 15–20 years but have instead a lifetime of below 10 years [7].

In order to solve the erosion problem (e.g., developing new coatings or better operational control), good understanding of blade erosion mechanisms and the linkage between the material properties, service conditions and erosion are required. In a series of works [7–9], the mechanisms of leading edge erosion and existing modelling techniques were investigated. For the estimation of pressure on the coating, the analytical water hammer equation and complex finite element (FE) models of the raindrop-coating contact and stress wave propagation in the coatings have been applied [4,10]. For the simulation of the raindrop fluid behavior, both Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) and Coupled Eulerian Lagrangian (CEL) approaches were used and compared with each other [12,13]. The SPH method was also used to model rain erosion in [22]. These models made it possible to vary a number of parameters, and thus, analyze their effects on the mechanical stresses during the impact event and study how they affect the erosion process. Various models have been used to analyze the fatigue damage and degradation of the coatings, including an analytical/phenomenological approach by [15] and computational finite element models [10–14]. In a number of studies, the effect of leading edge roughness on the blade aerodynamics was studied [16–18], using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and experimental methods.

Numerical modelling of the impact of a raindrop on a polymeric coating is a challenging task. It involves a complex fluid–structure interaction as well as complex viscoelastic and hyperelastic material behavior for the coating layer. Obtaining results of high quality requires fine meshes and significant computational times. The material behavior requires extensive testing for the FE model input parameters to be accurate. Rain erosion also causes a multiaxial fatigue state in the coating materials, where the loading direction changes with every impact. It must be noted that there still does not exist a well-accepted damage model for the coating materials used against rain erosion. Thus, prediction for lifetimes so far has been performed by using fatigue test data for the coating. These data are hard to obtain for high strain rates experienced during the impacts and standard rain erosion tests [21] are highly stochastic and are not well suited for measuring stresses or pressure during the impact.

It can be seen that most studies are devoted to solving one of two problems: (A) evaluating the effect of surface roughness on the energy generation in blades, and (B): prediction of coating lifetimes subjected to rain erosion. However, the link between the

degradation of the protective coating material and the roughness formation is seldom investigated.

In this paper, a computational model for the prediction of the roughness evolution of the protective coating layer is developed. The main purpose of this approach is to link fatigue properties of the coating with material removal and provide a 3-dimensional rough surface as an output. The rough surface can provide valuable input to aerodynamic simulations which predict the AEP loss for different leading-edge roughness states. The stresses of the coating are computed with a FE model that uses the CEL approach to capture the large deformations of the rain droplet and material removal occurs when fatigue damage at one point reaches a threshold value. A representative volume of the coating layer is discretized with points, where fatigue damage is calculated, and multiple droplet impacts are simulated on the surface. The fatigue properties of the coating material are estimated using inverse modelling, and data from rain erosion testing of the coatings. The model considers three assumptions:

1. The FE model simulates an impact on a flat surface and the stresses are not affected by roughness, once material has been removed.
2. Degradation and removal of the coating material are determined by local fatigue damage parameters. Local fatigue damage is associated with local material degradation due to growth of micro damage.
3. Faster damage accumulation is applied to areas where sharp edges are formed, assuming stress concentration in those areas. This is done because of the modelling challenges described in Section 3.2.

The output of the model is compared with measurements of surface roughness parameters obtained from a sample tested using rain erosion testing (RET). In Section 2, the FE model and fatigue damage calculations are described in detail. The material removal criterion and modelling are described in Section 3. Section 4 describes the method of extracting surface roughness parameters from a RET sample using an optical profilometer. Section 5 describes the process of calculating the fatigue properties of the coating and the time dependent surface roughness outputs. Section 5 also presents a discretization sensitivity study. Section 6 presents a comparison between the simulated results and the measurements. The conclusions of this study are presented in Section 7.

2. Rain droplet impact FE model and fatigue damage calculations from multiple rain droplet impacts

This section describes the FE model which is used to extract the stresses of the coating layer during a single rain droplet impact. The process of calculating fatigue damage and the simulation of a rain event over a small area of the coating are described.

2.1. Finite element model of rain droplet impact

A droplet impact event is simulated with the finite element (FE) method, using the commercial software ABAQUS [19]. The FE model consists of the water droplet and a representative volume element (RVE) of the leading edge protection (LEP) material.

To capture the large deformations of the water droplet, a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian model (CEL) is used, as in [12]. The LEP system is modelled using a traditional Lagrangian approach, while the water droplet is placed inside a volume that is simulated with the Eulerian approach. Inside that volume, the droplet is initially assigned water properties, and an initial velocity is applied to

it via a predefined field. A volume fraction tool is utilized to define the part of the Eulerian volume which must be filled with water. The initial velocity is taken equal to the tip speed of the blade at the position of interest. A linear Rankine-Hugoniot ($Us-Up$) equation of state is used to model the water behaviour. The Mie-Grüneisen constants of the $Us-Up$ equation of state are $C_0 = 1450m/s$, $\Gamma_0 = 0.5$ and $S = 2$. The water droplet has a density of $1000kg/m^3$, and dynamic viscosity of $8.9 \cdot 10^{-4} Pa \cdot s$. The LEP material was modelled with a combination of hyperelastic and viscoelastic properties, which is the considered representative of polyurethane based coatings. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and tensile test data are used to extract Yeoh hyperelastic parameters as well as Prony series parameters for the time-based linear viscoelastic definition. MCalibration [18] from PolymerFEM is used to obtain these parameters. The boundary conditions and mesh of the model are shown in Fig. 1.

A Dynamic-Explicit solver is used to simulate the impact. Reduced integration, 8-noded, 3D brick elements (EC3D8R) are used for the eulerian volume and C3D8R for the coating RVE. The droplet is placed at a small distance of $0.05mm$ above the RVE while there is a $0.5mm$ penetration of the Eulerian volume inside the RVE. A general contact formulation, with hard normal and frictionless tangential interaction properties is used to avoid convergence issues related to contact involving friction.

The dimensions of the RVE are chosen such that the edges are far enough from the point of impact so there are limited stress reflections from these edges. The edges are positioned four times the droplet diameter away from the impact centre. The depth of the RVE is $3mm$. A finer mesh is applied close to the point of impact as the stresses there must be captured with more detail. The smallest element size for all simulations is $0.05mm$ directly below the droplet. Convergence studies for stresses showed that stresses generally increase as the mesh size decreases. The mesh size of $0.05 mm$ for the fine area of the RVE was chosen so that the simulation time is acceptable. The mesh size of the eulerian domain is

also equal to $0.05 mm$. The total simulation time is calculated as $T = \frac{U}{2d}$, where U is the tip speed and d is the droplet's diameter. Studies carried out showed that this time duration is enough to capture the largest stress values during the impact. The droplet is assumed to be spherical initially. A built-in ABAQUS antialiasing filter is applied to the field output variables during the simulation to filter out fluctuations of stress values.

2.2. Extraction of stress values from the impact simulation

In this section, the procedure of using the stress output of the FE models to calculate fatigue damage due to a single impact is described. A number of paths that start from the surface of the LEP and extend to a chosen depth Z_{max} are defined. The vertical distance between two consecutive paths is denoted as dZ . All the paths start from the axis of impact and extend all the way to a distance where there is no effect from the impact. The general concept is shown in Fig. 2. Along those paths, stress values are extracted that will be later used to calculate fatigue damage.

The maximum depth Z_{max} should be chosen according to the depth of interest for damage calculation. Distance between two paths dZ should be small enough to allow accurate representation of the stress field. Due to the temporal variation of the stress field, a high enough sampling frequency must be chosen to accurately extract all the information from the analysis. For this study, 50 output intervals for stresses were chosen as the sampling frequency. The stresses are later post-processed with a python script. This way, a stress history is created for every point along each path.

2.3. Calculation of fatigue damage of the coating layer from the impact stresses

Rain erosion causes a multiaxial fatigue state in the coating material as the loading direction can be different for each stress cycle. In such cases, it is common to use equivalent stresses for

Fig. 1. Boundary conditions of the FE model (top), mesh of the coating layer (bottom left), mesh of the eulerian domain (bottom right).

Fig. 2. Stress extraction from FE models.

the calculation of fatigue damage, as described in [11]. In this study, the following procedure is used to account for the multi-axiality of the stresses during rain erosion: First, an equivalent stress such as the Von Mises or the Maximum Principal stress is used to create a stress history at each extraction point from all the time frames of the FE analysis. In cyclic fatigue loading, it is common practice to calculate the stress amplitude and mean stress values during each stress cycle[23]. The mean stress (σ_m) and stress amplitude (σ_a) are defined as:

$$\sigma_m = \frac{\sigma_{max} + \sigma_{min}}{2}, \quad \sigma_a = \frac{\sigma_{max} - \sigma_{min}}{2} \quad (1)$$

In this work, each water droplet impact is considered as one stress cycle, the mean stress is neglected and the stress amplitude (S_a) is calculated as the half difference between the maximum and minimum stress values calculated during the cycle:

$$S_a = \frac{\max(S_{eq}) - \min(S_{eq})}{2} \quad (2)$$

where S_{eq} is the equivalent stress history at the extraction point. So, in this way, only a single stress amplitude value is associated with each extraction position. Rainflow cycle counting is also an option, but in that case, more than one stress amplitude values are saved at each position. A comparison of the two methods is presented in a later section. Since each impact is considered as one stress cycle, the stress amplitude at each position corresponds to $N = 1$ for damage calculations. In that way, correlation with experimental RET (rain erosion tester) data is easier as these tests count the number of impacts or specific impacts to failure.

After the stress amplitude S_a is calculated for every position as described previously, damage can then be calculated by using Eq. (3), where N is the number of cycles with a stress amplitude S_a and N_f is the number of cycles to failure for that S_a . Each impact is considered as one stress cycle, so $N = 1$. To calculate damage d , the following equations are used. The formula for N_f is taken from [20] and is considered to be representative for polyurethane based materials.

$$d = \frac{N}{N_f}, \quad N_f = e^{\frac{S_a - b}{a}} \quad (3)$$

Here, a and b are LEP material parameters obtained from S-N curves from fatigue testing. Obtaining these parameters for the LEP material is not trivial as it is not an easy task to correlate stresses with number of impacts to failure. A method for calculating these values based on FE models and RET data is presented in a later section. An example of a damage contour plot of a single impact is shown in Fig. 3.

2.4. Fatigue damage calculation for multiple impacts

To simulate a rain event and calculate fatigue damage, a small volume of the coating material is discretized with a number of discretization points. These points are uniformly distributed along a rectangular grid over the whole volume of the coating layer. It is at those points, where fatigue damage is calculated by considering impact positions and the stresses from the FE simulation. The impact coordinates on the surface of the coating volume are sampled from a uniform distribution over a surface bigger than the surface of the coating. This is done in order to avoid edge effects in damage calculations. The difference between the dimensions of the area for impact coordinates sampling and the dimensions of the damage calculation area is equal to the FE model's maximum stress extraction distance. A total damage variable D is defined for each discretization point, where the damage from every individual impact is added:

$$D = \sum_i^N d_i \quad (4)$$

where N is the total number of impacts, I is the number of the current impact and d_i is the damage from the current impact. All impacts are assumed to occur at a 90-degree angle relative to the surface. After every impact, the following steps are taken to calculate fatigue damage at each discretization point of the coating:

1. The distance between each point and the impact is calculated.
2. The stress values from the FE model are interpolated based on the distance of the previous step.
3. Fatigue damage is calculated with the equations of Section 2.3.
4. Fatigue damage from the current impact is added linearly to the total damage variable of every point.

All the above are done with a Python script. For higher accuracy, a sufficient number of discretization points should be selected. To demonstrate the results of damage calculation over an LEP volume, a volume of $5 \times 5 \times 0.15 \text{ mm}^3$ was chosen with $N_x = 31$, $N_y = 31$ and $N_z = 31$ as the number of discretization points, along the x , y and z directions, respectively. The resulting damage contours are shown in Fig. 3. Maximum Principal stresses were used for the calculations.

To correlate with rain erosion testing, the specific number of Impacts NO or total impingement H can be extracted from the python script. The specific number of impacts NO is defined as the number of impacts per area of $\frac{\pi d^2}{4}$ where d is the droplet diam-

Fig. 3. Damage contours due to multiple impacts, top surface (A), cross section at point of maximum damage (B).

eter in RET. The total impingement H is defined as the total height of rain in mm that impacts the studied surface.

3. Modelling of roughness on the surface of the coating

This section describes the material removal criterion, based on fatigue damage values and the process of applying faster damage accumulation in areas where geometrical sharpness is formed.

3.1. Calculation of roughness from the damage distribution

During damage calculations for multiple impacts, the following method is used to estimate the roughness shape. If damage at a point is greater than 1.0, then material is removed at that position.

Otherwise, if damage is less than 1.0, then material is still present. If a point reaches damage values of 1.0 or greater, a damage value of 1.0 is assigned to it, to indicate that the area around the point is removed. The material is uniformly distributed within cells. The position of each cell is defined by the discretization point associated with it. The discretization point is positioned at the centre of the top surface of each cell. Maximum Principal stress values are used for modelling roughness as it is assumed that these stress values are responsible for the formation of surface cracks. During simulations, the choice of Maximum Principals stresses leads to damage initiating from the surface rather than below it. The output of the roughness prediction, when the above technique is used, is illustrated in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The predictions for roughness are created using a python script.

Fig. 4. Damage on the surface (A), cross sectional plot of the corresponding roughness shape for $x = 0$ mm (B).

Fig. 5. 3D roughness surface resulting from damage calculations.

In Fig. 4, the damage field over the surface and the resulting cross sectional roughness profile plot, at the middle of the surface, are illustrated. In Fig. 5, a 3D rough surface is generated by keeping the top-most points where damage is below 1.0.

At this point, it is necessary to note that this approach assumes that the impact conditions do not change as the surface starts getting rough. Thus, the stress values of each impact do not change due to roughness. This is obviously not correct and a way to adjust stress and damage values due to roughness should be included in the roughness prediction model. Nonetheless, this approach could still be effective in predicting the initial stage of erosion and providing a rough estimation of the actual roughness values.

3.2. Roughness effect on further surface degradation: new model

When a large number of impacts is experienced by the coating, the damage appears to be uniform over the surface, simply because if the rain lasts long enough, droplets will hit all of the surface.

However, once roughness forms, pits on the surface will create local stress concentration, when the stress wave propagate. It will lead also to quicker damage growth in these regions.

In order to take this effect into account, a special Python code was developed. The code analyses the surface, and identifies the regions, and points, where pits and concavities (with V-similar shape) were already formed, at the previous stages of loading. After every impact, the search algorithm is applied to detect all such areas that are affected by the impact. In the points of the “pit tips”, the effect of local stress concentration is taken into account by the introduced damage multiplication parameter K. This parameter, allowing for the damage multiplication effect due to available pits,

is applied to the current damage of the point at the tip of roughness using the following equation $d_{rough} = d^K$, where d_{rough} is the new damage value at the point and d is the current damage. The value of K must be less than 1 so that the new damage value is larger than the previous one. If the value of K is too small then damage and roughness depths will increase rapidly. Values between 0.9 and 1.0 will lead to the best results. Damage in unaffected areas is still accumulated linearly. A schematic of the areas where K is applied is shown in the top graph of Fig. 6.

In so doing, the effect of full material removal was also taken into account. Given that the top surface of the coating will be fully eroded at some time moment, the corresponding correction was introduced. Once a layer of points is fully eroded, the stresses experienced by every other point must be adjusted based on the new impact surface. This is important as stresses close to the impact surface are much larger than those further below it. A schematic of this effect is illustrated in the bottom graph of Fig. 6.

4. Experimental roughness measurements from rain erosion testing

The experimental setup and the scanning method used to extract roughness parameters from a curved test sample, are described in this section.

4.1. Rain erosion tests and roughness measurements

Rain erosion testing was carried out, and RET samples were used to calculate V-N curves and to take roughness measurements after the end of the test. The roughness parameters measurements

Fig. 6. Application of K in rough areas (A), schematic of new impact surface due to erosion (B).

Fig. 7. RET sample for roughness measurements (A) and 3D optical profilometer (B).

will be compared with the results of the numerical roughness calculation code.

Samples with a coating material of known DMA data were tested using a rotating arm test rig. In total, three samples of the same coating material were tested. The rain intensity during testing was 30 mm/s and the needles that were used generated droplets with diameters of 2.4 mm. The samples were tested for a total of 3 h which corresponds to a number of specific impacts

equal to 3556. All positions along the samples experienced the same number of specific impacts. Curves of velocity and specific number of impacts (V-N0) were created for the first signs of damage on the coating during testing. After the end of the test, roughness measurements from one of the samples were taken with the help of a 3D optical profilometer. The sample and the optical profilometer are shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 8. Roughness measurements for a velocity close to 140 m/s (A), 150 m/s (B).

The sample was chosen for roughness measurements as it did not exhibit severe erosion or full coating removal in many places. The 3D optical profilometer is made by InfinityX. DeltaPix software was used to scan the surface and get roughness measurements at different radial positions along the sample. For roughness measurements, an area close to the leading edge was defined using the mentioned software. The measurements were taken at a relatively flat portion of the leading edge of the sample and in places where the scans were not influenced by edge effects. The area size over which roughness measurements were taken were kept as constant as possible between measurements. An illustration of the measurement technique is shown in Fig. 8. The vertical distance between each measurement was 1 μm .

Roughness parameters R_a , R_z and S_a , S_z were measured according to the standard ISO 4287:1997. R_a , S_a are the average roughness over line and surface measurements respectively. R_a , S_a are the average roughness over line and surface measurements respectively. R_z , S_z are the averaged maximum peak to valley heights, over line and surface measurements respectively. Measurements were correlated with velocity through the rotational speed of the sample. The impact velocity is assumed to be almost equal to the tip velocity of the sample. The measurements are shown in Fig. 9.

Only the damaged sample was available to the authors for measurements and thus it was not possible to measure the initial surface roughness of the sample. It would be an interesting study to

compare the roughness values before and after the test, to test the effect of initial roughness on further erosion of the coating layer.

Areas further away from the root of the sample, where tip speeds are higher, had larger roughness values. In some cases, measurements were influenced by large pits where erosion broke through the coating layer and continued into the putty or composite layers. These pits could be due to defects such as voids inside the coating. Roughness parameters in those areas were quite large, especially for tip velocities in the range of 150 – 160 m/s.

5. Computational simulations

In this section, simulations were performed with the developed model and the outputs are presented. A proposed method to calculate the fatigue properties of the coating based on RET data is described first. The next part compares computing stress cycle counting using the rainflow method, with the stress amplitude equation presented in Section 2. Finally, the outputs of the model and a discretization sensitivity study are described.

5.1. Determination of input data: inverse simulations to determine the fatigue properties of coating material

Among other input parameters, the fatigue curve (number of cycles to failure versus stress, so called S-N curve) is the parameter, which is most difficult to determine. Using tensile fatigue data might lead to poor lifetime predictions as rain erosion involves different damage and fatigue mechanisms than tensile or shear loading.

Here, we propose a new way of extracting S-N curve by inverse modelling of RET data using FE modeling. This method utilizes impact velocity – cycles to failure (V-N) curves and a small number of a single droplet impact FE models for different impact velocities, which are determined by the velocity range of RET data. The main principle is that FE models are used to relate stress values to velocity values and then generate S-N curves by replacing velocity values of the V-N curves from RET. The steps of this method are:

1. A power curve is fitted to the RET curve for N_0 to incubation versus tip speed.
2. A number of points along the curve are selected and N_0 to end-of-incubation is calculated with the fitted curve.
3. FE models with an impact speed determined by the above points are created and stresses are extracted.
4. Droplet impact coordinates are generated around a point of interest for each tip speed as in Fig. 10A.
5. S_a values experienced by the point of interest are saved for every impact until the corresponding N_0 to end-of-incubation is reached, for each tip speed case.
6. Damage expressions are created for each tip speed with a linear damage accumulation rule and with the use of an S-N curve equation: $S_a = a * \ln(N) + b$. Each impact corresponds to one stress cycle.
7. The damage expressions for each tip speed are inserted into an optimization loop that tunes a and b until all damage expressions are equal or close to 1.

After all the above steps are performed, an estimation of the S-N curve parameters is obtained. During stress extraction from the FE model, stresses are saved for different depth values and therefore only the maximum damage value for all depths is taken into account for calculating the S-N curve parameters. It is necessary to state that there is a stochastic nature in calculating stress ampli-

Fig. 9. Measurements of roughness parameters R_a and S_a (A), R_z and S_z (B).

Fig. 10. Calculation of stress amplitudes from random impacts schematic (A), resulting damage output versus impact velocities from optimization of S-N curve parameters (B).

tudes as the impact positions are generated randomly. There is less statistical variation with a large number of specific impacts.

5.2. Determination of fatigue curve using inverse modelling and RET testing: Example

To demonstrate the application of the above method, a case study is performed for the available RET data. Sample number 2 is used for curve fitting to the RET data by using Matlab in Fig. 11. From curve fitting a power law, the specific number of impacts to failure for velocities of 130 m/s, 140 m/s, 150 m/s and 160 m/s are calculated. Finite element models of a single impact are constructed for the mentioned velocities and for a droplet diameter of 2.4 mm. DMA data of the coating material is available and required to create the FE models. For each velocity, stress amplitude values are saved for the corresponding number of impacts to failure. To do that, a script is created using Python. Then, damage is calculated with the damage equation stated before and the S-N curve parameters are calculated using SciPy's minimize function. SciPy automatically determines the best solver for this optimization problem and no constraints are set for the parameters. An initial guess of the parameters is made by a grid search over a range of the parameters. The best combination of parameters is chosen as the initial condition. The solver displayed some inaccuracies for some of the velocity values, as shown in Fig. 10B, but the solution is considered acceptable.

The calculated S-N curve parameters are then used in reverse-mode inside the python script to perform lifetime estimations. The end-of-life condition is met when the damage parameter

Fig. 11. RET data for S-N curve parameters calculation (A), Predictions vs. RET data with the optimized S-N curve parameters (B).

reaches a value of 1. The predictions are tested against RET data for sample number 3 in Fig. 11. The lifetime calculation is performed 3 times for each velocity to check the reproducibility of the results.

The predictions seem to be good in the range of 140–150 m/s but there is no datapoints close to 160 m/s. Results from the 3 different runs of the predictions are similar so the results are reproducible. RET data shows large scatter and S-N curve parameters could be calculated with higher confidence if experimental data were more consistent. The proposed method could be extended by using rainflow cycle counting for each impact. It is good practice to perform multiple stress amplitude history calculations for each velocity as the impact positions are generated randomly and might lead to different S-N curve parameters. Extra parameters could be fed to the optimization loop, such as a mean stress correction parameter for the stress amplitude, so that a better fit to the experimental data can be obtained.

5.3. Effect of cycle counting vs. no cycle counting on damage

The damage calculation technique described previously (Eq. (2)) is compared to damage calculations by using rainflow cycle counting in the left and middle contour plots of Fig. 12. The contour plots illustrate the damage field calculated by using the Maximum Principal stresses for a single impact.

Fig. 12. Damage contours with cycle counting (B), without cycle counting (A), with cycle counting and $N = 1$ (C).

Fig. 13. Maximum damage values comparison between cycle counting and no cycle counting.

From the contour plots it can be observed that the damaged positions do not change but the damage values have significant differences. Damage values are much lower when rainflow cycle counting is used. The maximum damage values are summarized in a bar chart in Fig. 13.

Despite S-N curve parameters being calculated without considering cycle counting, the damage values should be close if the approximation of holds. However, damage values are different between the two cases. Damage values are smaller for the case of

cycle counting due to the rainflow technique counting the number of cycles equal to 0.5 for most stress amplitudes, instead of 1.0. In the approximation for S_a , one impact is considered as 1 stress cycle. The calculated stress amplitude values by the rainflow cycle counting technique are not much different than when only the maximum and minimum stresses are considered for calculating stress amplitude. This results in damage values almost 2 times smaller when the S-N curve parameters, S_a values and the corresponding cycle counts are fed to the damage calculation equation (Eq. (3)).

To directly compare cycle counting versus the S_a approximation technique, rainflow cycle counting is used but the number of cycles is equal to 1.0 for all stress amplitudes counted. The comparison is illustrated in Fig. 13. Now damage values are almost identical, showing that the S_a value can be calculated with the proposed method. The resulting damage contour plots for $N = 1.0$ are illustrated in Fig. 12. Damage values are almost the same, as well as the location of higher damage areas.

5.4. Generation of rough surfaces

The goal of the roughness modelling method is to create rough surfaces on the coating due to rain erosion, which can be used to study the degradation of the aerodynamic performance. That is achieved by finding all the points with damage values less than 1 and creating a 3D contour plot in Python. The results for the case of 150 m/s for various values of N_0 , to monitor the progress of erosion throughout time, are presented in Fig. 14. The surfaces monitor the evolution of erosion from the first sign of damage up to the final value of $N_0 = 3536$.

Fig. 14. Rough surfaces for $V = 150$ m/s.

5.5. Curves of roughness parameters and mass loss over time

It is possible to monitor the values of Ra and Rz throughout time by outputting their values at different numbers of specific impacts. This is performed for Rz for the three tip speeds examined in Fig. 15A. For the calculations K was equal to 0.995. Values of Rz are zero during the incubation time and they become larger as erosion progresses. The curves for 150m/s and 160m/s conclude to identical Rz values despite having different incubation times, indicating that the tip speed of 150m/s could lead to worse roughness conditions.

Mass loss per unit area can also be calculated for different values of specific impacts. This is done by calculating the ratio of failed points to the initial number of points and then multiplying by the initial mass of the studied coating volume. For the calculations a density of $1000 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$ is assumed for the coating material. Again, $K = 0.995$. The results are presented in Fig. 15B. It is observed that higher tip speed values lead to higher material removal rates.

5.6. Effect of discretization on results

To test the sensitivity of the results on the number of discretization points, the roughness parameter values Ra and Rz are calculated for 4 different number of points along a line. The number of points were 11, 21, 41 and 81 for the four cases and the average of three simulations is used for the comparison. The results are presented in Fig. 16. The tip speed examined is 150m/s with $K = 0.995$. There is some variation in the results for different cases that could be due to the randomness of the rain field, but in general the predictions seem to be independent of the number of discretization points. Values of Ra seem to vary more than values of Rz when the number of discretization points is changed.

6. Comparison between simulations and experimental measurements

This section presents a comparison between the experimental roughness measurements and the simulated roughness parameters. The calculation of roughness parameters from the rough surfaces generated by the model, is also described.

6.1. Roughness prediction code parameters

For roughness predictions, three impact FE models with a droplet diameter of 2.4mm are run for velocities of 140m/s , 150m/s and 160m/s . The S-N curve parameters of the coating are calculated with the method described previously for the material tested in RET. The roughness code parameters and results are presented next.

The size of the studied area was 2mm by 2mm for the predictions. The vertical distance between points where damage is calculated was 5microns for a total depth of 0.15mm . Therefore, roughness predictions can be made with minimum accuracy of 5microns . Along the length and width direction, 21×21 points were used. In RET, each position on the sample experienced 3556 specific impacts, so random impacts were generated until a value of 3536 specific impacts was reached.

6.2. Calculation of Ra and Rz

Roughness parameters are calculated for the middle cross section of the generated rough surface, along the x axis. First, the middle line of the profile is calculated by linear least squares fit using numpy. Then the following equations are used to estimate the roughness parameters:

$$Ra = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i|, \quad Rz = |\max(y_i)| - |\min(y_i)| \tag{5}$$

Fig. 15. Evolution of Rz throughout time for all tip speed cases (A), Mass loss of the coating over time for all tip speed values (B).

Fig. 16. Predictions of roughness parameters for different discretization densities.

where y_i is the distance of each point of the profile from the mean line. No wavelength cut-off frequency is specified for the calculation.

6.3. Comparison of roughness values between measurements and predictions

The predictions of the roughness calculation code are compared against the roughness measurements of the RET sample. The comparison is performed based on the value of Rz and Ra. Two values of K are used for the predictions, 0.99 and 0.995. Predictions are made for three tip speeds of 140 m/s, 150 m/s and 160 m/s. The average of three predictions for each velocity value is used for the comparison. The comparison against RET roughness measurements is shown in Fig. 17. The values of Sz and Sa are also illustrated in the graph to compare against area measurements.

It is observed that the predicted Rz values increase rapidly between 140 m/s and 150 m/s but they are almost the same for 150 m/s and 160 m/s. The authors attribute this to a faster erosion of the top surface for the case of 160 m/s as the stresses near the surface are higher, leading to similar Rz values as for the case of 150 m/s. It is worthy to note that the predicted depth of erosion increases as the impact velocity increases. This leads to increased mass loss rates for larger impact velocities, as can be seen from Fig. 15B. Also, the smaller value of $K = 0.99$ results in larger Rz values than $K = 0.995$. The same holds for Ra values. RET measurements are affected by large pits that could be caused by defects in the coating, especially for velocities between 150 m/s and

Fig. 17. Comparison of Ra (A) and Rz (B) predictions against experimental measurements.

160m/s where some large roughness values are observed. The majority of the measurements for that velocity range lie within a smaller range of R_z and S_z values. The predicted R_z values are generally larger than this range and they seem to overpredict the measured values. A smaller value of K could lead to smaller R_z predictions. For the values of R_a , the predictions are close to the measured data for areas with large pits except for the tip speed of 150m/s. The predictions overpredict most of the measurements. Values smaller than $5\mu\text{m}$ do not provide accurate predictions as this is the vertical distance of the discretization during calculations. The predictions can provide a rough estimate of the measured R_z or S_z values, but this cannot be said for the values of R_a or S_a . The larger roughness values might correspond to defect driven failure of the coating. If these values are disregarded, it can be observed that R_z and S_z measurements below 100 μm and R_a and S_a measurements below 20 μm , give similar results for 160 and 150 m/s. This is in accordance with the trend predicted by the simulations.

It should be noted that the curvature of the specimen is not taken into account by the model. A flat test sample could be a more robust way to verify the proposed model and allow for more control over the impact angle and velocity.

7. Conclusions

In this paper, a computational model of the evolution of roughness on the blade's surface was developed, on the basis of fatigue damage and liquid impact simulations. The novel method for estimating the evolution of leading edge roughness of wind turbine blades due to multiple random liquid impacts has been developed, taking into account also the effect of formed roughness on the further surface degradation. The computational model has been compared with measurements from RET (rain erosion tester) experiments.

The new approach fills the gap in the computational analysis of blade erosion, linking the available continuum mechanical models of blade degradation (e.g., [10,12]) and available aerodynamic models of energy generation with rough surfaces (e.g., [5]).

In the computational studies, the effect of impact velocity on the roughness evolution was investigated. A finite element computational model of a rain drop impact on the polymer coating surface was developed with the coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian approach. Using surface fatigue damage simulations, the authors determine the roughness evolution on the surface of the wind turbine blade. Roughness is simulated by progressive material removal and sharp edges are assumed to introduce faster local damage accumulation. A simplified stress amplitude calculation method, which considers each impact as one stress cycle, was introduced and it showed similar results to rainflow cycle counting. A novel approach to evaluate fatigue properties of the coating material (S-N curve), based on RET data, inverse damage calculation and simulations of multiple raindrop impacts was developed.

The developed model was used to simulate the evolution of roughness for a RET sample, for which measurements of roughness parameters were performed with an optical surface profilometer. The comparison revealed that the model could provide results within the measured values, but there was a mismatch for the trends between the measurements and the predictions.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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